

EDUCATING MIDDLE-GRADE STUDENTS IN A NATIONAL SPIRIT THROUGH FOLKLORE-ETHNOGRAPHIC SONGS

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Annotation: This article analyzes the pedagogical significance and methods of educating middle school students in the national spirit through folklore and ethnographic songs. It is emphasized that folklore and ethnographic songs, as a rich cultural heritage of the people, serve as an important tool in forming a sense of national pride and identity in students. The article also highlights the educational potential of such songs and their role in the process of instilling national values in the minds of the younger generation. The effectiveness of educating students in the spirit of aesthetic taste, patriotism and respect for Uzbek culture through folk songs is scientifically proven.

Keywords: folklore and ethnographic songs, national spirit, educational opportunities, middle school students, national values, patriotism, cultural heritage, aesthetic education.

Introduction.

Each nation lives with its invaluable cultural heritage and preserves its identity by passing this heritage on from generation to generation. The rich folklore treasury of Uzbekistan, ethnographic songs formed over the centuries, reflect not only the feelings of our people, but also their life, traditions and national values. In today's era of globalization, the issue of educating the younger generation in the national spirit is becoming more and more relevant. After all, the fact that national values and cultural heritage occupy a strong place in the minds and hearts of the younger generation is of great importance in understanding who they are and forming their love for their homeland.

Folklore and ethnographic songs, with their deep spiritual content, aesthetic beauty and educational power, can awaken a sense of love, patriotism and national pride in the hearts of students. Through such songs, students are taught not only music, but also the history, lifestyle and values of the people. Today, under the influence of globalization, the problem of preserving nationality among students is emerging. In this situation, educating middle school students through folk songs performs not only a spiritual, but also a pedagogical task.

Therefore, this article analyzes the educational impact of folklore and ethnographic songs on students, their role and effectiveness in forming them in the national spirit. Experiences and recommendations in this regard make an important contribution to today's educational process.

Methodology.

The process of educating students in the national spirit through folklore and ethnographic songs requires a deep methodological approach. In this study, innovative approaches were developed based on the integration of pedagogical and musical education. First of all, the importance of conveying national values to students was chosen as the methodological basis. The use of folklore and ethnographic songs in the educational process was carried out taking into account the personal interests, age characteristics and needs of students.

Practical experiments and observation methods were used in the research process. Interactive methods were used in the classes with students, revealing the educational potential of folk songs. In particular, the goal was to instill national values through musical listening exercises, performance skills, analysis of the content of songs and discussions about them. At the same time, educational activities and thematic classroom hours were organized to provide a broader understanding of folk traditions and culture.

This methodological approach was aimed at increasing students' interest in music, developing aesthetic taste and bringing them closer to national culture. At the same time, group work, creative projects and role-playing games were used to involve all students in the class as active participants. These methods served not only to strengthen students' national pride, but also to develop their communicative and social skills.

In order to assess the effectiveness of these approaches, diagnostic methods were analyzed, including questionnaires, interviews and students' creative work. The results obtained showed the strong influence of folklore and ethnographic songs in the upbringing of the national spirit and further expanded the possibilities of using this methodology in the educational process.

Discussion.

Thinking about the importance of using folklore and ethnographic songs as a means of educating middle school students in the national spirit requires a deep analysis not only of the content of the educational process, but also of its impact on the future generation. As it was found out during the research, folk songs are not limited to the development of musical aesthetics, but also serve as

an important tool in instilling national values in the minds and hearts of students.

During the classes, it was observed that students approached the content of the songs with interest, felt a sense of national pride through historical events and heroic motifs in them. Understanding the meaning and significance of folk songs allowed students to understand not only the art of music, but also the customs, traditions and philosophy of life of their nation. For example, by analyzing the musical versions of the epic poem "Alpomish", students not only understood the uniqueness of national epic art, but also felt the patriotic ideas expressed in it.

The active participation of students also played an important role in increasing the effectiveness of the lessons. They got closer to national culture by performing folk songs, retelling related legends and stories, and demonstrating their creative interpretations. This process developed communication skills among students, strengthened teamwork, and encouraged them to share their culture with others.

However, some problems were also observed during the study. In particular, some students showed low interest in folk songs and less recognition of folklore music under the influence of modern music. To overcome this problem, it was determined that folk songs should be enriched with modern presentation methods and communication between them should be strengthened.

In general, the practical effectiveness of forming a national spirit in students through folklore and ethnographic songs has been confirmed. This approach serves as an important tool in increasing students' respect for national values, developing their educational and creative abilities. At the same time, the search for new methodological approaches to preserving and promoting folk musical culture will remain relevant in the future.

Conclusion.

Folklore and ethnographic songs are the spiritual wealth of the people, the heartbeat of their national culture, and their use in the education of the younger generation has created an opportunity to form a national spirit. As the study revealed, these songs play an important role not only in developing musical aesthetic taste, but also in forming in students a sense of patriotism, respect for national values, and an understanding of the rich cultural heritage of their people.

During the sessions, the content of folk songs successfully instilled cultural awareness and national pride in students. Their interest and active participation once again confirmed the importance of folk music in the process of national education. Through the analysis and performance of songs, students, along with an understanding of national identity, learned the history, traditions and values of their people.

At the same time, the importance of applying modern educational methods to folk musical heritage became clear. This will ensure that folk songs are more interesting and relevant for today's generation. The use of interactive approaches, along with modern technologies and creative developments in presenting folklore music, can further increase its educational effectiveness. In conclusion, it was shown that involving folklore and ethnographic songs in the education of students is one of the effective ways to preserve and develop national culture. This approach will remain relevant not only today, but also in the education of future generations. After all, attention and respect for one's cultural heritage are one of the most important factors in shaping the future of the people.

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